

Supporting information

Understanding pH changes and mitigation of mineral scaling in membrane capacitive deionization

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Table S1. Composition of different feed water solutions at pH 7.73 with experimentally measured ionic compositions. The concentrations of HCO_3^- and CO_3^{2-} are calculated using Aqion Pro software as mentioned in the method section.

Ion	Concentration (mM)		
	Tap water (pH 7.72)	Synthetic water (pH 7.73)	NaHCO_3 water (pH 7.73)
Cations			
Na^+	3.08	1.97	4.93
Ca^{2+}	0.79	1.92	-
K^+	0.08	-	-
Mg^{2+}	0.40	-	-
Anions			
HCO_3^-	4.43 (calculated)	4.63 (calculated)	4.89 (calculated)
CO_3^{2-}	0.014 (calculated)	0.015 (calculated)	0.015 (calculated)
Cl^-	1.05	1.02	-
NO_3^{2-}	0.06	-	-
SO_4^{2-}	< detection limit	-	-
PO_4^{3-}	< detection limit	-	-

Table S2. Current and discharging time during the discharging step in asymmetric desalination experiments.

Current (A/m^2)	Discharging time (s)	Equivalent WR %
5.93	300	27
7.41	240	33.5
9.88	180	44.5
11.11	160	50
14.81	120	67

Figure S1. The carbonic species distribution for desalinated water and for concentrate with pH calculated using Aqion Pro software.

Figure S2. The carbonate concentration and the effluent pH changes during a complete desalination cycle.

Figure S3. Unused and used spacer in tap water experiments; mineral scaling is observed on the used spacer.

Figure S4. A picture of a pristine AEM and an used AEM in tap water experiments; the colour change is clearly visible.

Figure S5. Predicted titration curve for the concentrate in NaHCO_3 desalination at 50% WR condition. The green highlighted area shows the buffer range with limited pH changes when HCl is dosed.

Figure S6. LSI prediction for concentrate composition of 90% WR tap water experiments as a function of pH (a), and of the Ca^{2+} concentration (b).